

INTERPRETATION OF THE DIRECTION OF LINGUOCULTURALISM IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK LINGUISTICS

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Abstract: This article provides information about the direction of linguocultural study in English and Uzbek linguistics. Today linguo-cultural studies are one of the main branches of anthropocentric direction, one of the leading paradigms in world linguistics. Linguo-cultural studies are the study of the relationship and influence of language with culture, ethnos, and national mentality on the basis of anthropocentric paradigm principles. The serious and systematic implementation of linguo-cultural analysis of language in Uzbek linguistics began in the second decade of the XXI century. During this period, linguo-culturalism began to take shape as a separate branch of Uzbek linguistics. Anthropocentric views of language played an important role in the formation of this industry.

Keywords: English and Uzbek linguistics, linguoculturalism, linguoculturology, national value, linguoculturema, cultural background, cultural heritage, cultural process, cultural space, cultural fund.

Introduction

Each nation reflects certain national traditions. That is, every nation has its own national traditions and customs. In this sense, every person is related to a specific culture, language, history, literature that reflects this nationality. It is known that language, being a social phenomenon, is inextricably linked with culture. Today, economic-political, cultural and scientific relations between people, peoples, countries, international cultural communicative processes in the field of linguistics, such as the interaction of languages and language culture and the national identity of the language,

and between cultural studies is causing the emergence of a new field with a specific direction and subject - linguoculturalology. Linguoculturology is a separate scientific field that studies the phenomena that reflect the integral connection of "language and culture", its formation and development - language and culture together. It is a general science that arose between the sciences of cultural studies and linguistics, and studies phenomena such as the interaction and connection of language and culture, the formation of this connection and its reflection in language and outside language as a whole system is engaged in learning.

Linguoculturology as a special field of science has given rise to a number of productive concepts in modern linguistics: lingvoculturema, cultural language, cultural text, cultural concept, subculture, linguocultural paradigm, cultural universality, cultural potential, cultural heritage, cultural traditions, cultural process, cultural process instructions, etc. Also, the main conceptual apparatus of linguoculturology includes mentality, rituals, images - customs, cultural sphere, type of culture, civilization, paganism and others. The most important of these concepts are cultural sema, cultural background, cultural concept, and cultural connotation, which can be expressed through the linguistic units of cultural information. Cultural semantics are semantic units, semantic characters that are smaller and more universal than words. For example, the following cultural semantics can be distinguished in the words palov, do'ppi, o'choq: Palov- Uzbek national dish made of rice, carrots, meat, onions and butter: Do'ppi - rectangular Uzbek national hat: O'choq is a device in which a fire is lit and a boiler is mounted on top for cooking.

Findings and methods

Cultural background is a description of nominative units (words and phraseologies) that represent social life and historical events. For example, the legacy of Daqqiyunus // Adam's legacy is very old, ancient ", jamalak comrade" childhood friend ", red (used as a word for belonging to the October Revolution, the Soviet regime, the army). two types of information are present in the denotation and are well

studied in linguistics. Because cultural concepts are the names of abstract concepts, here cultural information is attached to the signification, the core of the concept.

Cultural heritage is the transfer of cultural riches and information that are important for culture.

Cultural traditions are a set of valuable elements of social and cultural heritage.

A cultural process is an interaction of elements related to a system of cultural events.

Cultural space is a form of cultural existence in the minds of representatives of culture. Cultural space is related to cognitive space (individual and collective), because it is formed by a set of all representatives of this cultural-national society, all individual and collective spaces. For example, Russian cultural space, English cultural space, etc. The linguocultural paradigm is the ethnic, social, historical, scientific, etc., of the worldview is a set of language forms that reflect interrelated categories. The linguocultural paradigm combines concepts, categorical words, and so on. Language forms are the basis of the paradigm. Cultural tradition is an integral phenomenon that represents the experience of social stereotyped groups that accumulate and regenerate in society.

A cultural fund is a set of knowledge of a representative of a culture. some of his views on national and world culture. However, it is not the property of an individual, but a set of those basic units that belong to that culture.

Mentality is a manifestation of the worldview in the categories and forms of the mother tongue, which combines the intellectual, spiritual and volitional features of the national character. The unity of mentality is the concept of this culture. According to Gurevich, mentality is a way of seeing the world, it is not like an idea. Mentality is not a philosophical, scientific, or aesthetic system, it is a level of social thinking in which thought is inseparable from emotion. Folk mentality is relevant in important concepts of language. Mentality (German: mentalität<lot. Mens, mentis - mind, cognition) is the level of thinking, cultural potential of a society, nation, community or individual,

their ability to analyze the laws of life, mental ability in certain social conditions, mental strength. Mentality is a category that reflects the mentality of a people, the internal structure and differentiation of its mental and spiritual power.

According to the scientific literature, the term mentality refers to a deep mental structure that depends on sociocultural, linguistic, geographical and other factors. The mentality of a society, nation, or individual also includes their specific traditions, rituals, customs, religious beliefs, and superstitions. The language of culture is the formation of the structure of existing, or recreated imaginations, concepts, images, and other spiritual constructions through a system of signs and their relationships. Subculture is a secondary, dependent cultural system (for example, youth subculture, etc.). Cultural connotation is the interpretation of aspects of denotative or figuratively motivated meaning in the categories of culture. Cultural connotation is an indicator of the level of culture in a language sign. N. Yu. Shvedova singled out 20 categories of general meaning in Russian: vitality, action, state, object, dimension, place, time, and so on. These categories constitute the spiritual critique of language. However, there will also be specific figurative associative mechanisms that provide additional portable meaning for each nation. In recent years, linguistic and cultural issues have been thoroughly studied. According to V.V.Vorobev, "today, linguoculturology is the study of a set of cultural values selected in a certain way, the creation of speech and the lively communicative processes of its perception, linguistic personality and national mentality, which systematically provides a linguistic image of the world scene, education and knowledge acquisition, it can be noted as a new philological science that ensures the fulfillment of educational and intellectual tasks. Therefore, linguocultural science is a complex science that reflects the interaction and interaction of culture and language and this process as a whole structure of linguistic and non-linguistic units. [1]

Studying the relationship between language, culture, and ethnicity is an interdisciplinary problem. The solution to this problem can be solved only with the

joint efforts of several disciplines, from philosophy and sociology to ethnolinguistics and linguocultural studies. For example, linguistic philosophy with ethnic issues of linguistic thinking, psycholinguistics with specific linguistic aspects of ethnic, social or group communication, etc. is engaged in. Linguoculturology emerged as an independent branch of linguistics in the 90s of the 20th century. According to researchers, the term "linguculturalology" (lat. lingua "language", cultus "respect, bow", Greek "science") was coined by the Moscow phraseology school headed by V.N. Telia appeared in connection with the research. The subject of linguculturalology is language and culture, which are in close contact with each other. Linguistics is a new field of language research formed at the intersection of cultural studies and linguistics. Lingvokulturology studies the interaction of culture and language, the interaction of which is reflected in the language of the people's culture. Cultural science (culturology) studies the self-awareness of a person in his social and cultural life according to nature, society, history, art and other areas. Linguistics studies the human worldview, which is reflected and recorded in language in the form of mental models of the linguistic landscape of the world.

Linguoculturology is closely related to ethnolinguistics and sociolinguistics. Even, according to V.N.Telia, linguo-culturology is a component of ethnolinguistics. However, both linguoculturology and ethnolinguistics are separate disciplines in their essence. The roots of ethnolinguistics begin with V. Humboldt in Europe, go back to the researches of F. Boas, E. Sevir and B. Warf in America, D.K.Zelenin, Ye. F. Karsky, A.A.Shakhmatov, A.A.Potebnya, and others in Russia. V.A.Zveginsev described ethnolinguistics as a direction that studies the relationship of language with the social structure of society or the culture, traditions, and customs of the people. In the center of modern ethnolinguistics are the elements of the lexical system of the language that interact with specific, material and cultural-historical complexes: cultural forms, customs, traditions. This direction can be divided into two separate branches: 1) reconstruction of ethnic areas according to language; 2) reconstruction of the material

and spiritual culture of the people according to language data. [2] Human culture consists of a collection of different ethnic cultures aimed at satisfying the same need in different ways. Ethnic identities, including how people work, how they rest, how they eat, how they talk, etc. appears everywhere in different situations.

According to N.I. Tolstoy, the goal of ethnolinguistics is to reveal the folklore scenery and stereotypes of the peoples of the world.

Sociolinguistics is a branch of linguistics that studies language and its relationship to the social conditions in which it exists. Social conditions are the set of external conditions under which the actual language develops: the society of people using this language, the social structure of this society, the age, social status, culture and education level of the language owners, the differences between the places of residence, as well as the differences in their speech behavior depending on the communication situation are understood. So sociolinguistics is a field of linguistics that studies issues related to the role of language in the life of society, its social nature, social functions, and the mechanism of influence of social factors on language.

In linguistics, by the end of the 20th century, the hypothesis that "language is not connected with culture, but is itself a tool that grows out of culture and represents it" was accepted. At the same time, language is a means of creation, development,

preservation (in the form of texts) and its component of culture. Because material and spiritual works of culture are created through language. On the basis of this idea, linguoculturalism, which has been formed for thousands of years, was created in the 90s of the 20th century as a new, special field of science. Linguistics is a product of the anthropocentric paradigm in linguistics, which has been developing over the last decades. V.A. Maslova divides the development of linguistics into three periods:

1. The creation of preliminary studies that are the basis for the formation of science.
2. Formation of Linguistic Culture as a separate field of research.
3. Emergence of linguistic and cultural studies as a fundamental, independent science.

Results and Discussions

By the beginning of the 21st century, linguistics has become one of the leading directions in world linguistics. Linguoculturology studies folk culture that is reflected and consolidated in language and discourse. First of all, he studies the myths, legends, customs, traditions, traditions, customs, symbols, etc. of a particular culture. These concepts are related to culture, and they are reinforced in the language in the form of household and food behavior. According to V.N.Telia, linguoculturology is primarily a study of living communicative processes and the relationship of language expressions used in it with the mentality of the people in synchronic movement. Linguistics is a science that studies language as a cultural phenomenon, and language and culture in interaction form its product. Consequently, V.N. Telia writes about this: "Linguoculturalism is a science that studies the human, or rather, the cultural factor in a person. This means that the center of linguoculturalism is a complex of achievements typical of the anthropological paradigm about a person who is a cultural phenomenon". [3] According to G.G. Slisshkin "Linguistics is focused on the human factor, more precisely, the cultural factor in a person. The fact that the center of linguoculturalology consists of the phenomenon of culture indicates that the science of man is a

phenomenon belonging to the anthropological paradigm”.[4] N. Alefirenko describes linguoculturology as follows:

- linguoculturology is closely related to linguistics and cultural studies, and it has a synthesizing nature;

- linguoculturology focuses on cultural evidence that is explained in language;

- linguoculturology is part of the linguistic sciences, so its research results can be used practically in the process of teaching mother tongue and foreign languages;

- the main directions of linguocultural studies: a) linguistic personality; b)

language is a system of semiotic embodiment of cultural values.[5]

Several directions have been formed in linguoculturology until today:

1. Linguoculture of specific social groups, people's cultural relations in the visible period, that is, research of specific linguocultural situations.

2. Diachronic linguoculturology, which studies relevant linguistic and cultural changes of the people in a certain period.

3. Comparative linguoculturology, which studies the linguistic and cultural manifestations of different peoples interacting with each other.

4. Cross-cultural linguistics. It has now begun to develop and has been reflected in various studies. For example, M.K. Golovanivskaya studied the features of the French mentality from the point of view of a Russian language and culture owner in her research entitled "French mentality from the point of view of a Russian speaker". As analysis material, fate, danger, luck, soul, conscience, thought, idea, etc. in Russian and French languages. abstract nouns served.

5. Linguocultural lexicography, which deals with the compilation of geographic dictionaries.

Among those mentioned, one can see the active development of the last direction. For example, D.G. Masleva's dictionary includes 25 thematic sections. They include Germany's geographical realities, climate, flora and fauna, history, customs, traditions, legends, aphorisms, various holidays and ceremonies, religious beliefs, currency,

measurement unit, industry, trade, science and language units representing technique, art, education, national dishes, normative monuments, national character, etc. are reflected. On the basis of such dictionaries, the relationship between language and culture can be thoroughly studied.

Conclusion:

In linguocultural studies, it can be seen that the following issues are mainly studied: 1) linguocultural characteristics of a specific speech genre. In this, the language of myths, genres typical of folk art is studied; 2) study of the expression of the linguocultural concept in a work written in a certain style. In this, the language of artistic prose works is analyzed; 3) comparative studies. In this case, more units of the Russian language are compared with English, German, and French languages; 4) aspects of linguocultural science related to the science of pedagogy. The purpose of this is to identify and analyze linguocultural units for pupils and students in social sciences. As a result of the above analysis, linguo-cultural studies has emerged as a separate field in Uzbek linguistics. Today, Uzbek linguo-culturology is one of the independent disciplines with its own scientific apparatus. The most important achievement of such research is that language has been interpreted as an accumulative phenomenon that connects generations, embodies the culture and spirituality of the people, and the connection of language with culture is illustrated by the example of the Uzbek language.

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